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PRE PRODUCTION FOR DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATIONAL 3D ANIMATION ACCORDING TO VEJNOVIC MODIFICATION OF THE CESAREAN SECTION TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Computer Graphics can be used for educational, interdisciplinary presentations and for visualization purposes, as it represents an ideal means to teach any discipline that could benefit from the visual presentation. Everyone needs visualization because it is the most natural way in which people view the world, hence the well-known saying that "a picture is worth a thousand words". Visualization represents an excellent choice for presentation in studying and teaching, as well as in information transfer. Engineering Animation is used as a presentation technique. It can be an important link between an idea and its realization like building a model/object.

In this paper, we will show all the necessary techniques used in the process of creating 3D Computer Animation which are prepared to assist in the education and virtual training of Medical Doctors. We are in charge of the development of 3D Computer Animation according to professor Vejnovic's modification of the cesarean section technique. The process of creating 3D animation will be shown using a couple of examples. Also, the procedure and the list of steps that need to be followed in this specific case to create a 3D animation for educational purposes will be shown.

Keywords: Computer Graphics; Animation for Educational purposes; Cesarean Section technique

1. INTRODUCTION

Educational animations are animations produced for the specific purpose of fostering learning. The popularity of using animations to help learners understand and remember information has greatly increased since the advent of powerful graphics-oriented computers. This technology allows animations to be produced much more easily and cheaply than in former years. Previously, traditional animation required specialized labour-intensive techniques that were both time-consuming and expensive. In contrast, software is now available that makes it possible for individual educators to author their own animations without the need for specialist expertise. Teachers are no longer limited to relying on static graphics but can readily convert them into educational animations.

The first educational animations were created around the middle of the 20th century and were two-dimensional.

The Story of Menstruation [1] is a 1946 10-minute American animated film produced by Walt Disney Productions. It was commissioned by the International Cello-Cotton Company and was shown in a non-theatrical release to approximately 105 million American students in health education classes. In 2015, it was selected for preservation in the National Film Registry (USA).

Donald in Mathmagic Land [2] is a 27-minute Donald Duck educational featurette released on June 26, 1959. The film was made available to schools and became one of the most popular educational films ever made by Disney. As Walt Disney explained "The cartoon is a good medium to stimulate interest. We have recently explained mathematics in a film and in that way excited public interest in this very important subject".

There are many technical animations, for example, *3D movie - how a car engine works* [3]. This animation describes the working principles of engines in the context of an inline-four engine that operates in a four-stroke mode. This kind of engine has four cylinders mounted in a straight line.

Jose Arce and Oscar Ivanisevich, two famous surgeons, wanted an animated film showing the technique of their work. To learn and see what needs to be animated Quirino Cristiani had to attend operations [9]. He agreed to that on condition that they ensure him a strong drink. He made two movies: *Gastrotomia* (1925) and *Rinoplastia* (1925) which Sorbonne University later bought for educational purposes. The films were praised for accuracy and realism.

The aim of this paper is creating a storyboard as a final step in the pre-production of the animation which presents the procedure for closure of the uterine incision according to Vejnovic's modified technique of caesarean section ([6], [7]). Namely, there are different approaches in the uterine closure and some of them pass with minor complications [8].

A storyboard is a graphic organizer in the form of illustrations or images displayed in sequence for the purpose of pre-visualizing a motion picture, animation, motion graphics or interactive media sequence [5]. The storyboarding process, in the form it is known today, was developed at Walt Disney studios during the early 1930s, after several years of similar processes being in use at Walt Disney and other animation studios.

The topic of the paper is not a medical one, it is mainly technical. We obtained the initial data by making a high-resolution film in which a doctor – surgeon, instead of repairing of the uterus, sews two pieces of sponge. There are several reasons for this: first, when sewing the sponge the whole procedure was performed in a relaxed atmosphere, the doctors did not hurry. We had time to ask questions and discuss some aspects in order to adequately understand the problem and the procedure. Another reason is that with real repairing of the uterus there is a lot of blood which certainly reduces the visibility and transparency. Precisely because of the bleeding, in real life the doctors must perform the whole procedure in the shortest period of time and there is no time for discussion and asking questions. The third reason is that the procedure is carried out by two doctors who stand on either side of the patient with other medical personnel also present in the operating theatre so it is a very crowded scene. The position of the camera in such a situation would be bad and would, therefore, result in a bad footage.

Once we captured the sewing of the sponge, from a few iterations, which included drawing storyboards and consultations with the doctors and then making corrections to the storyboard, we produced the storyboard presented in this paper.

An integral part of the storyboard are corresponding comments related to individual drawings. Our intention was that every reader of this paper regardless of whether they are a medical professional, but especially if they are a doctor, understands the procedure of repairing the uterus with caesarean sections using Vejnovic modification.

Experienced doctors surgeons have realized that new technologies such as computer animation can provide new tools for the education of young gynaecologists who come to specialize at the Clinic for Gynaecology and Obstetrics in Novi Sad, Serbia. That was the underlying idea for forming our team combining the expertise of doctors - gynaecologists and professionals who deal with computer visualization [4], especially computer graphics. The ultimate goal of this project is to create a 3D computer animation in which the described procedure of repairing uterus will be animated. With storyboard, the pre-production procedure is completed for creating new animations.

2. STORYBOARD OF VEJNOVIC MODIFICATION OF THE CESAREAN SECTION TECHNIQUE

Figure. 1: First step of the repair of the uterus

There are four columns (1, 2, 3 and 4) and three rows (A, B and C) on each Figure shown in this text. That means each figure is composed of maximum twelve pictures: A1,..., A4, B1, ..., B4, and C1, ..., C4.

According to Vejnovic modification of caesarean section, there are four steps in closing the uterus incision. We will present all the steps through eleven figures.

In Figure 1 we can see the following details:

Picture **A1** shows that first step of repair of the uterus is starting.

A2: A uterus incision is represented with an opening which is approximately 10 cm long. Top view is presented;

A3-4: Needle and surgical thread are presented; for better visibility of the drawing, the needle holder is not drawn.

B1: Starting position of the initial stitch is approximately 2cm medially from the angle of the incision and 1cm cranially from the cutting surface of the uterus.

B2: A needle and a thread penetrating through the anterior uterine wall.

B3: Cross-section of the anterior uterine wall is shown. Front view is presented. The uterine wall consists of three layers: *perimetrium* (outer layer), *myometrium* (middle layer), and *endometrium* (inner layer). In B3 *endometrium* is the bottom layer and is painted in blue. *Myometrium* is approximately 90% of the total thickness of the uterus and is painted in red.

B4: The entire cross-section is shown in grey except the part of *myometrium* that is coloured red. This red part of *myometrium* is the part through which we wish (intend) to go out with the needle from the intersection. The reasons for this attitude are of medical nature.

C1: Needle goes out from the right part (position at the picture) of the intersection.

C2: Needle goes to the left part of the intersection. Needle point passes by the outer layer (*perimetrium*) of the left cross section.

C3: The body of the needle pushes downwards (untwisting) *endometrium* which is rolled up, until the point of the needle takes place in the level of *myometrium* that corresponds to the opposite side of the uterine wall. The segment on the left cross section where we want the point of the needle to penetrate into the left section is coloured red.

C4: The needle is correctly appointed.

Figure. 2: Creating initial suture

A1: The needle correctly penetrates *myometrium* and *perimetrium* on the cross section (the points of needle penetration should be at the same depth in *myometrium* and same distance at the *perimetrium* surface).

A2: Important note: THE NEEDLE MUST NOT PASS THROUGH THE *ENDOMETRIUM!*

A3: If the needle passes through the *endometrium* then incision site gets everted (*endometrium* is directed to the outer layers of the uterine wall). In that case, the sutured segment becomes thinner compared to the surrounding wall of the uterus. The picture on the right of A3 shows the proper suture. In that case, the sutured segment becomes thicker or equal compared to the surrounding uterus wall thickness. Hypothetically this can reduce the risk of uterine rupture and placental complications.

A4: Three variations of the thicknesses of the uterus are shown: δ shows the normal thickness of uterus, δ_1 is the thickness of the uterus in poor joining ($\delta_1 < \delta$) and δ_2 is the thickness of the uterus in good joining ($\delta_2 > \delta$).

B1: The trajectory of the needle is presented.

B2: Free end (without needle) of a thread is left in the length of around 20cm.

B3-4: Both sides of the thread are pulled together in the same direction and tightened by hand (this is done by the surgeon).

C1: The intact part of the uterine wall next to incision angle becomes visualized and approachable for suturing.

C2-4: Needle is inserted into the intact part of the uterine wall, approximately 2cm laterally from the first stitch and about 0.5cm (up to 1cm) from the angle of the incision. Hence, the starting position of this stitch is approximately 2cm laterally and 1cm cranially (position of the stitches is in the same horizontal line as the first needle positioning).

Figure. 3: Creating the first knot

A1-3: Making the second stitch.

Important note: Position of the second stitch is near the angle of the incision!

A4: There are two sides of the thread, one is with the needle, the other is free.

B1: Tying the knot with instrument. The thread (the side with a needle) is wrapped twice around the needle holder, clockwise.

B2: With the tip of needle holder the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

B3: The thread is wrapped once, clockwise, around the needle holder.

B4: With the tip of the needle holder the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

C1: For the second time the thread is wrapped once around the needle holder, counter clockwise. With the tip of needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

C2: We can say that the knot is locked. The knot created in this way is considered safe.

C3-4: The free end of the thread (which is without needle) is marked with *Pean* instrument.

C4: Temporary situation. *Pean* instrument is hanging from the right side of the patient.

Figure. 4: Making the first running-locked suture

A1-3: The running-locked suture starts with the stitch which is 1-2cm medially from the initial suture and around 1 cm cranially from the cutting surface (1st running-locked suture).

A4: Pay attention to the trajectory of the thread. The thread should create a loop as it is shown. The succeeding stitch (2nd running-locked suture) is made with the same interspace (1-2cm medially from the nearest suture and around 1 cm cranially from the cutting surface).

B1: The 2nd running-locked suture is finished and the 3rd running-locked suture is started with the same interspace (1-2 cm medially from the nearest suture and around 1 cm cranially from the cutting surface).

B2: The 3rd running-locked suture is finished.

B3-4: Tying the knot with instrument. The thread (the side with a needle) is wrapped twice around the needle holder, clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of thread are pulled in the opposite directions.

C1: Distance between the initial suture and 3rd running-locked suture is approximately 5cm before tightening both threads and creating the final knot.

C2: The surgeon tightens the threads by pulling the two parts of the thread in the opposite directions.

C3: By tightening the thread, the distance between the initial suture and the 3rd running-locked suture is reduced.

C4: The distance between the initial suture and 3rd running-locked suture is approximately halved and it is now about 2.5cm long.

Figure. 5: Finishing the first step and starting the second step of the repair of the uterus

A1-2: Locking the knot. The thread is wrapped once around the needle holder, clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

A3-4: For the second time the thread is wrapped once around the needle holder, counter clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened. This side knot is locked now.

B1: The free end of the thread (which is without needle) is marked with the same *Pean* instrument and left hanging from the right side of the patient.

C1: The second step of repair of the uterus starts.

C2-4: Repetition of the sequence A3-4, B1 from Figure 1 at the opposite angle of the incision.

The whole procedure that will be shown in Figures 6 and 7 is the same as the 1st step of the repair of the uterus, except everything happens as a mirror image. We can say that 1st and 2nd step are axially symmetric, where the axis of symmetry is the vertical line which is located in the middle of the uterine incision.

Figure. 6: Second step - creating initial knot on the opposite angle of the incision

Figure. 7: Making running-locked suture on the opposite angle of the uterine incision

Figure. 8: Third step of the repair of the uterus

A1: The appearance of the operative field after the 1st and 2nd step are finished.

B1: The third step of repair of the uterus starts. It includes suturing of the remaining central part of the incision.

B2: Suturing is continued using the needle and thread from the **right** side (left side of the incision from the patient's view). Running-locked sutures are made.

B3: Every new stitch is made approximately 1-2cm medially from the last suture and around 1 cm cranially from the cutting surface.

B4: The same suturing principle is used until reaching the central part of the incision. Pay attention again to the trajectory of the thread. The thread should create a loop as it is shown.

C1-3: The sequence B2-4 of this figure is repeated on the opposite side of the incision. Now we have the following situation: there are two threads (green and yellow) in the middle, each ends with a needle.

C4: With these two threads surgeon ties a knot manually (left thread on the scheme is making loop around the right thread)

Figure. 9: Making a knot in the central part of incision

A1: One more knot is made in the same way (the left thread on the scheme makes a loop around the right thread).

A2-3: The distance between the two sutures in the central part of the incision is approximately 2cm before tightening the thread.

A4: The thread is tightened and the distance is reduced.

B1: The distance between the two sutures in the central part of the incision is **now** approximately 0.5-1cm

B2-3: Another knot is tied manually (the right thread on the scheme is making a loop around the left thread)

B4: The final knot is tied manually (left thread on the scheme makes a loop around the right thread)

C1-2: The central knot is created and locked

Figure. 10: Fourth step of the repair of the uterus

A1: The fourth step of repair of the uterus starts.

A2-4: There are four threads, two of them are in the middle and end with a needle, one free end originates from left side knot and another free end originates from the right knot.

The left thread from the middle is wrapped twice around the needle holder, clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the left free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of thread are pulled in the opposite directions.

B1-2: Two sides of the thread are tightened and the distance between the two sutures is reduced.

B3-4: Locking the left knot. The same thread (with a needle) is wrapped once around the needle holder, clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the same free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

C1: For the second time the thread is wrapped ones around the needle holder, counterclockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

C2: The final left knot is locked.

C3-4: The right thread from the middle is wrapped twice around the needle holder, clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the right free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions.

Figure. 11: Finishing the repair of the uterus

A1: Two sides of thread are tightened and the distance between the two sutures is reduced.

A2-3: Locking the right knot. The same thread (with a needle) is wrapped once around the needle holder clockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the same free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of the thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

A4: For the second time the thread is wrapped once around the needle holder, counterclockwise. With the tip of the needle holder, the free end of the thread is grasped. Two sides of thread are pulled in the opposite directions and tightened.

B1: This is the final right knot.

B2: All knots are locked. There are two pairs of thread ends.

B3: Using scissors two ends at the right side are cut.

B4: Using scissors two ends at the left side are cut.

C1: Operative field appearance after the repair of the uterus is completed.

Recapitulation

C2: The uterine incision at the start was approximately 10 cm long. After the suturing the length of the uterine incision is reduced to approximately 5cm.

C3: This is cross-section view demonstrating the effects of two suturing techniques on the length and thickness of the uterine incision. Two results are presented – a poor one (top picture) and a good one (bottom picture).

Important notes:

Bad result (Fig. 11, C3, top picture) **would occur if the needle passes through the *endometrium* while suturing.** In the standard technique of uterus repair, at the end of the process, the incision is as long as the initial incision.

Better result (Fig. 11, C3, bottom picture) **is obtained if Vejnovic modification of the cesarean section technique is performed:**

1. **In this case, the length of the incision is approximately halved.**
2. **It is particularly important in reducing the risk of complications in the subsequent pregnancies.**

CONCLUSION

This paper provides a brief overview of the use of 2D and 3D animations for education in various fields. The main topic of this work is creating a storyboard in which Vejnovic modification of repairing uterus at caesarean section is shown. Namely, it was noted in modern gynaecological practice that the possibilities for good and quality education of new doctors and residents are almost exhausted. On the other hand, experienced doctors have noticed that some of the disadvantages of the standard process of education can be overcome by the use of new technologies. This is where animation, a new tool in education which has several advantages, can help. The animation does not happen in the operating theatre where doctors and surgeons do not have enough time to teach because they have to operate and complete the operation at the optimum time. The animation of this process offers an opportunity to a young doctor to repeatedly see the operation on the screen, and with the animation many segments of the operation can be enlarged or shown in slow motion, and the whole procedure can be watched a countless number of times. This offers multiple benefits, to experienced doctors and even more to the younger ones. This practically means that a young doctor will be present at the real operation only when they become familiar with almost the whole procedure in the virtual world and after that, during the actual operation, they will be able to remove all doubts in consultation with an experienced surgeon. On the other hand, the time an experienced surgeon needs to be spent on the education of young doctors is significantly reduced and the process of education increases significantly in efficiency and speed and therefore in the quality.

This paper presents a detailed storyboard which is illustrated in 11 figures, each with a maximum of 12 pictures. An integral part of the storyboard are the detailed comments, which should clarify the situation to every reader. The storyboard is created based on the film showing a procedure of repairing the uterus by using a sponge model instead of a uterus. This is done in order to achieve a better shot than with a video of real operation conditions. It shows the surgical procedure without haste, in a relaxed atmosphere along with many significant comments on the details of the operation that a surgeon could emphasize and repeat. This also avoided blood on the scene, which in real terms reduces the transparency of the recording. In this way, the pre-production of the process of repairing the uterus by a modified Vejnovic technique is completed and our next job will be to create an educational 3D animation on this topic and thus complete the idea.

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